

ISic3347

I.Sicily inscription 3347

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building

Material

limestone

Object

architrave

Editor

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Principal Contributor

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Autopsy

2006.04

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tyndaris

Place of origin (modern)

Tindari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Tindari, Antiquarium di
Tindari

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645591

EDCS 70901003

Bibliography

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Gentili, G.V. 1952. 1821. Scavi nella città. *Fasti Archaeologici*. 5 (1950): 164-165.

Manganaro, G. 1965. Ricerche di antichità e di epigrafia siceliote. *Archeologia Classica*. 17: 183-210. At 203 no.1 tav.72.3

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